

Schools4energy: a living laboratory for energy awareness in schools

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Category: Research in-progress

Abstract

Schools4energy is a laboratory of sustainable experimentation for the implementation of good practices that aims to promote conscious and virtuous energy behaviours and energy efficiency in the schools. The activities, developed in the framework of the INTERREG MED PrioritEE project, involve the students, the teachers and the staff personnel of Primary and Lower Secondary Schools of the Municipality of Potenza. The Schools4energy laboratory is made up of three integrated modules (School race, Artists for energy, Energy at stake) based on different methodologies (analytical methods, co-creation and gamification) in order to increase the interest and the involvement of students and enhance their preferences and talents. The proposed activities pursue multiple objectives: to increase students' knowledge and skills on energy, to raise awareness on energy consumption, to encourage energy consumption reduction, to promote behavioural changes.

Keywords: *Multi-stakeholder engagement, Actors Motivation for Sustainable Actions, Public Schools, Energy Efficiency, Behavioural changes, Awareness raising*

1 Introduction

Living Labs are becoming increasingly popular to encourage an active engagement of citizens through experimentation and learning as well as to support a participative and inclusive decision-making process promoting by this way a faster transition towards a low carbon society.

According to the JPI Urban Europe, that firstly introduced the term Urban Living Lab – ULL they can be defined as “a forum for innovation, applied to the development of new products, systems, services, and processes, employing working methods to integrate people into the entire development process as users and co-creators, to explore, examine, experiment, test and evaluate new ideas, scenarios, processes, systems, concepts and creative solutions in complex and real contexts” (JPI Urban Europe, 2013).

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) defines Living Labs as “user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings. LLs are both practice-driven organisations that facilitate and foster open, collaborative innovation, as well as real-life environments or arenas where both open innovation and user innovation processes can be studied and subject to experiments and where new solutions are developed. LLs operate as intermediaries among citizens, research organisations, companies, cities and regions for joint value co-creation, rapid prototyping or validation to scale up innovation and businesses. LLs have common elements but multiple different implementations.”

Living Labs actually constitute a powerful form of governance that promotes cooperation through active participation, experimentation and learning representing a valuable tool to support a structured cooperation among local authorities, citizens and scientific institutions.

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), the international federation of benchmarked Living Labs in Europe and worldwide, provides many examples of Living Labs on different themes among which more than twenty examples corresponding to the key words “Energy”, “Efficiency” and “Renewable”.

Starting from the valuable background of the ENoLL and the experience gained by the authors in Interreg IVC RENERGY project (Dvarioniene et al, 2015), in the framework of the INTERREG MED PrioritEE project “*Prioritise energy efficiency measures in public buildings: a decision support tool for regional and local public authorities*” (PrioritEE, 2018), the Local Living Labs (LLLs) were adopted to boost the effectiveness of policy and measures and to facilitate the achievement of higher energy efficiency targets through an active engagement of stakeholders. The

objective of the PrioritEE Local Living Labs is twofold: on one hand to support an improvement in the energy performance of public buildings by monitoring their energy consumption and highlighting technical weaknesses, on the other hand to promote energy awareness in the whole community through experiential activities and the active involvement of public buildings users.

Three rounds of Local Living Labs (LLLs) were thus planned in each of the five partner regions (Karlovac County - Croatia, Municipality of Potenza - Italy, Region of Western Macedonia - Greece, Lezíria do Tejo Intermunicipal Community - Portugal, and Aragón region - Spain) according to the specific activities foreseen in the relate pilot case studies. In this framework, LLLs are very useful to gather information on the needs and expectations of public building users as well as to promote energy efficiency and awareness measures in the public buildings of pilot areas involving decision-makers and addressing energy managers and building users as main stakeholder for the implementation of energy saving measures. Customised activities have been organised in each community in close cooperation with the Local Authorities in order to capitalise their main outcomes in the local planning framework. An overview of the PrioritEE Living Labs is reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Overview of the PrioritEE Local Living Labs in the pilot areas

PrioritEE Partners	Target Area	Title and Aim	Stakeholders	Role
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National Research Council - Lucanian Energy Company - Municipality of Potenza 	Potenza Municipality (IT)	Schools4energy: experiential activities for awareness raising and energy saving in schools.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mayor - Municipal Staff - SEL (central energy purchasing body) - Energy managers -Headmasters - Teachers & Students -NGO (Legambiente) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy makers - Technical experts - Day-to day users - Executors of experiential activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Regional Development Agency of West Macedonia - Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving 	Region of Western Macedonia (EL)	Success Stories and Good Practises on energy efficiency: implementation in the Municipal Public Buildings.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National and Local Stakeholders - Representatives of the technical departments of the municipalities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy Makers - Technical experts - Executors of Good Practices
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - North-West Croatia Regional Energy Agency - City of Karlovac 	City of Karlovac (HR)	Success Stories in City of Karlovac: implementation of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mayors - Municipal Staff - Other public stakeholders - Civil society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy Makers - Technical experts - Executors of Good Practices

		selected good practices/awareness raising measures within the community.		
- Diputación Provincial de Teruel - University of Zaragoza	Teruel Province (ES)	Success Stories adapted to rural areas: implementation of customised solutions to improve EE in Municipal Public Buildings.		- Policy makers - Technical experts - Executors of Good Practices
-Leziria do Tejo Intermunicipal Community -Faculty of Science and Technology - NOVA University of Lisbon	Leziria do Tejo Intermunicipal Community (PT)	Training on the implementation of good practices and awareness raising measures: hands-on session on the energy management software recently installed on 46 municipal public buildings and implementation of selected good practices for the promotion behavioural changes in the target communities.	- Mayors - Energy managers - Municipal Staff	- Policy makers - Technical experts - Executors of Good Practices

2 The LLL of the Potenza pilot

This paper focuses on the Italian pilot case study (Municipality of Potenza) aimed at boosting energy efficiency in public schools run by the municipality. In fact, as well known, schools' energy bills represent a main source of expenditure in the economic budgets of municipalities. Their huge energy consumption is due to outdated and inefficient buildings and waste of energy caused both by a generally bad energy management (in particular, concerning heating) and the unaware users' behaviour. The students of Primary and Lower Secondary schools were identified as the recipient of the Living Lab activities. This was due to the primary necessity to reduce the schools' energy bills by triggering the attention of day-to-day users on energy awareness and to exploit the potential of young generations that can transfer the energy saving concepts on the whole community through family and friends.

Innovative and challenging educational activities based either on the use of different methodologies and tools were designed to trigger the attention of building users on energy themes while promoting an “energy saving” culture and a more efficient use of energy resources. In particular, cloud-based business analytics services will be utilised for energy consumption monitoring (Benchmark® and Power BI - <https://powerbi.microsoft.com/it-it/>), whereas co-creation (Rowley et. al, 2007) and gamification (<http://www.gamification.it/>) will allow to enhance the creative and playful components of the Living Lab. The long experience carried out by the Province of Treviso in the framework of the projects Interreg MED EduFootprint (<https://edufootprint.interreg-med.eu/>) and Interreg CENTRAL EUROPE TOGETHER (<http://www.interreg-central.eu/Content.Node/TOGETHER.html>), provided inspiration for organising a set of awareness raising activities engaging Local Authorities, teachers and students.

In the Potenza pilot Living Lab, schools will compete to achieve the highest savings either in term of energy uses and energy bill. Awareness measures will be adopted to support the decrease of consumption, assessing the role of consumers’ behaviour in energy savings. In parallel, interdisciplinary thematic activities will be developed to promote an improved knowledge on energy subjects through creative thinking and group dynamics. It is important to underline how this experience, by exploiting the interest of young people and their influence on the whole community, energy efficiency can be pursued while ensuring sustainable behaviours.

The Schools4energy project and its educational relevance has been designed in the framework of the Interreg Med PrioritEE project (PrioritEE, 2018) by CNR-IMAA and the Lucanian Energy Company, in collaboration with the Municipality of Potenza. It has been thought as a laboratory of sustainable experimentation in which users and energy experts cooperate to implement a user-driven innovation process through the Living Lab tools. The activities aim at promoting conscious and virtuous energy behaviours through the engagement on a voluntary basis of students and teachers of the schools owned by the Municipality of Potenza (Kindergarten, Primary and Lower Secondary schools). The aim is to foster an improved knowledge of energy issues and the energy bill, driving the attention of all the buildings’ users on how the behavioural changes can influence consumption. The energy topics will be inserted by the teachers in the curriculum of the school year 2018-2019 and, according to the outcomes of this experience, the method shall become an integral part of the education method in the schools operationally involved in the implementation phase. The experience is aimed at consolidating an “energy culture” in the context of education through a practical involvement of all the users of public schools and, in particular, pupils of different ages. Different methodologies and activities were integrated to foster a larger participation and encourage pupils, teachers and staff personnel to adopt "responsible" behaviours. Schools4energy is thus designed as an

experiential laboratory for the implementation of a systematic educational program that aims at:

- Improving the understanding of the value of energy and behavioural changes
- Supporting the creation of "energy natives" within the young generations
- Providing intrinsic motivations to improve energy uses by an awarding mechanism (such as having a recognition or prize);
- Improving/creating a sense of community (the users are protagonists / group effect);
- Making evident energy savings obtained from behavioural changes and quantifying them in energy and economic units;
- Supporting the creation of routine habits to be transferred in the family context and in the whole community.

From an educational point of view, Schools4energy contributes to four fundamental objectives:

- To promote an energy efficiency culture by highlighting the effects of the reduction of consumption deriving from behaviour, through experimental measurement and creative thinking
- To value economically the savings in the energy bill by adopting virtuous behaviours
- To promote environmental protection by reducing the pollutant emissions and energy waste through a conscious use of energy resources
- To improve the scientific knowledge and skills providing the basic elements to understand in detail energy consumption and energy bill by direct measurement and comparative analysis.

To valorise the interdisciplinary context as well as to exploit different attitudes and creativeness, three different groups of activities were designed (Figure 1):

Figure 1. The Schools4energy modules

The initiative will be presented to the school board prior of the beginning of the school year, in order to allow the integration of the foreseen activities in the educational curricula. In this regard, educational guidelines on “self-regulation” of consumption will be published to document the relevance of the initiative and to promote the dissemination of good practices in other schools.

A dedicated webpage to Schools4energy will be created on the institutional website of the Lucanian Energy Company to enable a direct interaction with the community and to provide information on the ongoing activities.

3 The Energy Team

As successfully carried out in the framework of the Green schools competition (<http://www.greenschools.it/homeen.aspx>) of the Province of Treviso (Italy) and the EURONET 50/50 MAX project (EURONET 50/50 MAX), each participating school of the Potenza Municipality will set up an **Energy Team** with coordination and control functions, as shown in Figure 2:

Figure 2: Energy Team components

School staff personnel with different roles and selected students will compose the school energy team. The external energy experts will train the school energy teams on the implementation of energy awareness activities. The school energy team will propose a set of energy saving measures (*“Decalogue of good practices”*) to be implemented in order to evaluate the influence of behaviours on energy consumption. Selected students of the Lower Secondary schools will act as facilitators to motivate their peers.

4 Energy Benchmarking: School Race

The *School Race* module, designed by SEL, represents the central element of the Potenza pilot Living Lab, supporting through a competition mechanism an increased knowledge on energy consumption, improved skills in science and technology and encouraging virtuous behaviour.

To motivate students and increase their interest, the participating schools are associated to the Formula 1 stables and the various buildings complexes of each institute will represent the pilots.

The match between the participating schools and Formula 1 stables will be carried out during an opening ceremony that will be held at the beginning of the 2018/2019 school year.

Two web-based tools are utilised to monitor energy consumption, share the results and show the energy trends:

- SELbench (Benchmonitor®), an innovative software implemented by the Lucanian Energy Company for monthly management of electricity and gas consumption, as well as Energy Benchmarking, available free of charge for all the affiliated public administrations³⁵, including schools,
- Power BI a business analytics service provided by Microsoft that allows for interactive visualizations with self-service business intelligence capabilities (<https://powerbi.microsoft.com/it-it/>).

To reduce their consumption and improve their position in the ranking of “Formula 1 stables”, each school will apply its “Decalogue of good practices” in a 7-month period (from October 1st, 2018 to April 30th, 2019).

Schools will be classified according to their features (age of construction and volume, equipment, number of users, etc.) and average energy consumption in energy levels (“BenchClass”). Their monthly consumption (natural gas for space heating and electricity) will be monitored on a 12-month period (May 1st, 2018- April 30th, 2019) and compared with a baseline, according to the reporting template shown in Table 2. Key Performance Indicators will be used to normalise the data in order to allow the comparison among schools with different features.

Table 4. Energy consumption monitoring template.

<i>School Year 2018/2019</i>			
School			
Address			
Energy Level (“BenchClass”)			
Month	i (i= May 2018 to April 2019)		
Electricity consumption		Natural gas consumption	
Point of Delivery Number (POD)		Redelivery Point Number (PDR)	
Total Electricity (kWh) – baseline <i>Month i</i>		Total gas (m ³) – baseline – baseline <i>Month i</i>	
Total Electricity (kWh) measured - <i>Month i</i>		Total gas (m ³) measured - <i>Month i</i>	

³⁵ SelBench is the Lucanian version of the software called Benchmonitor®, a system for tracking, visualizing and managing energy bill and energy consumptions, marketed in Italy through the portal www.controllabolletta.it.

Energy saving percentage (Variation between actual monthly consumption with the baseline)		Energy saving percentage (Variation between actual monthly consumption with the baseline)	
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An energy benchmarking procedure is applied to define the baseline consumption and to evaluate the energy savings. For each school, the energy baseline is represented by the average monthly energy consumption of the last three school years (2015/2016, 2016/2017, 2017/2018). Energy savings are evaluated by comparing the actual monthly consumption with the baseline.

A different involvement of pupils in the School race was devised according to their age and educational purposes, as reported in the following.

Level 1: Kindergarten and Primary School

The pupils of each class, coordinated by their teachers and assisted by the staff personnel will put into practice the “Decalogue of good practices” to decrease consumption. The observance of the Decalogue rules will be monitored weekly and the class will receive accordingly a green or red sticker corresponding to a positive or negative score (e.g. green sticker: +10 points; red sticker: -5 points). A monthly energy report will show the “efficiency” of each class and make evident their progresses. The energy reports will contribute to the overall school ranking.

Level 2: Lower Secondary School

The Lower Secondary School students will be involved actively in consumption monitoring and reporting. The students of each participating class will become part of the Energy Team and will be trained together with the teachers and staff personnel in the use of the ICT tools for energy benchmarking.

Monthly updated information on the ranking of “F1 stables and pilots” will be published on a dedicated page of the Lucanian Energy Company website to keep alive the interest on the race. A “School Race poster” will be displayed in each participating school to explain the initiative and the rules of the game. A QR code will provide the users with the possibility to deliver up-to-date information on Schools4energy initiative and schools ranking (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Data management and visualisation

A reward system based on the total savings obtained and the equivalent money earned by each participating school (a percentage of the energy bill savings) is defined in agreement with the Municipality of Potenza to award the school that will achieve the overall highest energy savings in the school year 2018-2019. The absolute ranking of the schools will be presented in the final awarding ceremony in May 2019.

5 Co-creation: Artists for Energy

Co-creation was identified as a powerful methodology to integrate energy issues in the educational curricula, promoting an interdisciplinary cooperation of teachers, valorising creativeness and involving a larger number of pupils.

A set of activities has been proposed to the school board for inspiration among which drawing and literary thematic competitions, creation of storytelling, posters on energy themes and energy saving measures, energy laboratories (construction of small energy toys – e.g. solar cars, solar boats, etc.), "energizing" musical performances; theatrical performances and sport competitions, addressed to children of different ages.

The teachers will define the thematic activities to be implemented during the 2018/2019 school year according to the different educational curricula and sections (Kindergarten, Primary, Lower Secondary) in order to maximize their educational

potential and encourage children to think about energy in a creative way.

A cooperation with local associations and NGOs (e.g. Legambiente) is envisaged to take advantage from their expertise and involve the community as much as possible. The artefacts made by the pupils by age group and category will be voted through the School4energy webpage on the Lucanian Energy Company website and the best ones will be rewarded.

6 Gamification: Energy at a stake

The role of gamification in supporting behavioural changes and motivation through evoking gameful experiences is widely studied and applied in many disciplines (e.g. Hamari J. et al., 2014; Kazhamiakin R. et. al 2016). This concept was exploited also in the context of many European funded projects that developed free downloadable thematic videogames, most of which can be used by teachers to drive the attention of students.

As alternative energy awareness activities, video games can encourage players to consume less energy, support behavioural changes and awareness raising through an alternative educational tool based on the concept of serious games.

In the Potenza pilot Living Lab framework, videogames were identified as alternative way of learning. The teachers will examine the proposed examples in order to plan their possible integration in the educational activities.

Table 3 reports the selected videogames concerning the energy themes.

Table 3. Thematic videogames on energy and environment

Project	Game/website	Objective
EnerCities IEE Project	EnerCities http://www.energycities.eu	Create and expand virtual cities capable to manage pollution, energy supply, renewable energy, etc.
Impact HUB Berkeley	Energy Chickens http://energychickens.weebly.com/	To decrease electric energy consumption of the building inhabitants
TRIBE H2020 project	Tribe.it http://www.tribe2020.eu/	To minimize the environmental impact of cities by reducing carbon emissions and building energy consumption

7 Calendar of activities

The Potenza pilot Living Lab activities have been developed since December 2017 according to the timeline reported in (Figure 4)

Figure 4. Timeline of the Potenza pilot Living Lab and School4energy activities

The public events will be jointly organised by the PrioritEE scientific partners (SEL and CNR-IMAA), the Municipality of Potenza and the schools to boost their communication power.

At the beginning of the 2018/2019 school year, an opening ceremony will officially launch the initiative. During the period October 2018 – May 2019, the schools will be also involved in thematic public events on energy awareness raising to reinforce motivation. In particular, it is highly recommended the participation in "M'illumino di Meno", a national symbolic initiative launched in 2005 by the radio broadcast Caterpillar of Rai Radio 2 and sponsored since 2015 by the Italian Ministry of Education, which is organized annually around the 16 February, date of entry into force of the Kyoto Protocol (Wikipedia, 2018).

The awarding ceremony will conclude the activities, emphasising the positive outcomes of the initiative. In particular, an exhibition of the creative works will be organized and the winners of each category will be awarded. The final ranking of the school race and the total savings earned by each school will be presented, and the winning school will be announced. In order to raise motivation and involvement, as well as to enhance the value of learning and participation, all the pupils will receive a certificate of participation acknowledging their commitment as "energy saving expert". A selected group of pupils will be also invited to participate in the PrioritEE Final Conference to present their experience emphasising its relevance in an international context and enabling networking initiatives.

8 Acknowledgements

This research was carried out in the framework of the project PrioritEE “Prioritise energy efficiency (EE) measures in public buildings: a decision support tool for regional and local public authorities” (Project Number: 1MED15_2.1_M2_205, Duration: 01/02/2017-31/07/2019). PrioritEE was funded under The Interreg MED Programme 2014-2020; Priority Axis: 2. Fostering low-carbon strategies and energy efficiency in specific MED territories: cities, islands and remote areas. We would like to thank the Municipality of Potenza (Italy) for its active role and continuous support as Associated Partner.

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